

USE OF SMART TECHNOLOGIES IN TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article discusses the methodology of developing smart teaching in the field of technological education. Also, theoretical and practical recommendations are given on the direction of technological education and training other students to the Smart education standard.

Keywords: Smart education, technologies, knowledge, teacher and business, teaching, book content.

INTRODUCTION

Smart education is not considered a standard in many countries, what is its main idea? In response to this question, it is necessary to see the development of approaches to education. It can be divided into three conditional stages, based on 5 things to see: knowledge, technology, teaching, teacher and business. Yesterday, if the source of knowledge for students was a teacher, a student could learn only in the auditorium, if he expanded his knowledge only through books, now this process is taking a different form in the West and in Russia and Uzbekistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the past, the purpose of universities was to train specialists for industrial production. "Now" knowledge is transferred not only from teacher to student, but also from student to teacher. This allows to create a new level of knowledge. Now the student can transfer knowledge not only to the audience, but also to the

Internet, remote tools, and sites. In this, educational technologies can be used. "Tomorrow" will be the Internet as the main source of knowledge for students, technologies will be directed to the creation of individual new knowledge. The teaching process involves the movement of knowledge objects in arbitrary directions from student to teacher, from student to student and vice versa [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The graduate is not only an expert in his field, but enters the business environment or education as a business partner or entrepreneur and an expert in education. In the previous decade, a digital society with such attributes was formed, for example, knowledge economy, e-army, e-government, e-culture, e-education, e-health, e-science. E-learning has penetrated into the digital society and is considered its central, system-creating element. But when it comes to e-learning, it is mainly based on technologies. Today, the base of leading universities has reached such a level that changes in it cannot bring about significant changes. It is no exaggeration to say that they have reached their peak. E-learning can no longer be an innovation, there are no unknown aspects in it. Access to content for students, feedback between teachers and students, communication of knowledge between them, all these are included in technologies. What's next? What do people do with these technologies? These questions belong to the field of Smart education. This field contributes to the high level of organization of education, which in turn responds to the issues and opportunities of today's world in the ever-changing environment, helps to move from book content to active content [2].

Smart education is the unification of educational institutions and teaching staff on the basis of common standards agreements and technologies to implement the process of mutual education on the Internet. Here we are talking about the creation of mutual content and its use. An example of this is a project in the European system of education. A European university with a single common

deanery, which in turn transfers students from one university to another The Bologna process gives the right to admit students without exams, thus creating a Smart education system for Europe. A single European university implements a collective process of education, which is managed from a single common repository of educational materials. Smart education is globally flexible learning in an interactive learning environment that is open to the public. The key to smart education is wide licensing of knowledge.

The goal of smart education is to transfer traditional education to electronic education and increase the efficiency of the educational process. Such an approach can help the teacher copy knowledge and make it accessible to each student. In addition, it helps to expand the principles of education, not only in terms of the number of students, but also in terms of indicators in time and space. 'lim remains licensed anywhere and everywhere. One of the conditions for the transition to smart e-learning is the transition from book learning to active learning. Booked content is converted to active content. Values in electronic form can be given with the greatest efficiency. In this case, knowledge should be located in a single repository, that is, an intellectual system of search. related objects should be interrelated with metadata. The quality of the repository should always be monitored before the implementation of such e-metrics systems, and should work in unity with the tracks that control the educational process. Smart education - Smart education means education that is carried out through special content organized on the basis of smart technologies or through a Smart book, for example, learning the basic concepts of the subject from Wikipedia through a Smart phone. An example of a smart book view is Wikki, Wikipedia. An electronic textbook is a textbook that consists of pictures, animations and tests, can be viewed in a web browser, and can be displayed on a computer. Electronic educational resources - educational resources in the form of visual materials, theoretical and pictorial materials, presentations, tables created in Word, Excel,

Power Point for use in the educational process. Electronic form of educational resources. For the development of smart education, it is necessary to ensure the production of technical tools related to this field of education: computers, mobile phones, tablets based on modern and advanced technology, placing smart-books, smart-educational books in them.

CONCLUSION

And so:

- Smart- electronic board has special buttons, through which you can draw different figures and lines.
- Smart is a convenient tool for modern remote and e-learning, including an electronic textbook.
- Smart - home-solar battery-based home heating and energy supply, implemented on the basis of human-sensing technology.
- Smart-city-solar-powered city, traffic lights powered by solar-powered batteries.
- Display videos related to this industry.

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